

VESSEL IDENTIFICATION

#	DMA Vessel Name	IMO Number	Wave	Designation Date	Total Flag Changes
1	N Cerna	9289520	Wave 1	25.06.2024	1
2	Angara	9179842	Wave 1	25.06.2024	0
3	Maria	8517839	Wave 1	25.06.2024	0
4	Saam FSU	9915090	Wave 1	25.06.2024	2
5	Koryak FSU	9915105	Wave 1	25.06.2024	1
6	Kavya	9353113	Wave 1	25.06.2024	3
7	Apar	9402471	Wave 1	25.06.2024	1
8	Legacy	9339337	Wave 1	25.06.2024	1
9	Saga	9318553	Wave 1	25.06.2024	1
10	Serenade	9318541	Wave 1	25.06.2024	2
11	Success	9333436	Wave 1	25.06.2024	1
12	Lady R	9161003	Wave 1	25.06.2024	0
13	Maia-1	9358010	Wave 1	25.06.2024	0
14	Hunter Star	9830769	Wave 1	25.06.2024	1
15	Daksha	9259185	Wave 1	25.06.2024	1
16	Enisey	9079169	Wave 1	25.06.2024	0
17	Kelly Grace	9331141	Wave 1	25.06.2024	1
18	Ozanno	9394935	Wave 1	25.06.2024	1
19	Delvina	9331153	Wave 1	25.06.2024	1
20	Bodhi	9144782	Wave 1	25.06.2024	0
21	Lunar Tide	9277735	Wave 1	25.06.2024	3
22	Dashan	9299666	Wave 2	17.12.2024	1
23	Sputnik Energy	9256602	Wave 2	17.12.2024	2

24	Alissa	9273052	Wave 2	17.12.2024	1
25	Marabella Sun	9323376	Wave 2	17.12.2024	1
26	Christophe de Margerie	9737187	Wave 2	17.12.2024	1
27	Altair	9413547	Wave 2	17.12.2024	2
28	Peta Lumina	9296391	Wave 2	17.12.2024	3
29	San Damian	9274331	Wave 2	17.12.2024	1
30	San Cosmas	9274343	Wave 2	17.12.2024	2
31	Monte Bianco	9385233	Wave 2	17.12.2024	1
32	Galaxy	9826902	Wave 2	17.12.2024	3
33	Rigel	9511533	Wave 2	17.12.2024	2
34	Cassiopeia	9341081	Wave 2	17.12.2024	2
35	Constellation	9306794	Wave 2	17.12.2024	2
36	Andromeda	9292204	Wave 2	17.12.2024	2
37	Callisto	9299692	Wave 2	17.12.2024	2
38	Alliance	9413561	Wave 2	17.12.2024	2
39	Phoenix	9333424	Wave 2	17.12.2024	2
40	Leo	9412347	Wave 2	17.12.2024	2
41	Zenith	9610781	Wave 2	17.12.2024	2
42	Turbo Voyager	9299898	Wave 2	17.12.2024	2
43	Sirius	9422445	Wave 2	17.12.2024	2
44	Saturn	9421972	Wave 2	17.12.2024	2
45	Oasis	9265756	Wave 2	17.12.2024	2
46	Yuri Senkevich	9301419	Wave 3	25.02.2025	1
47	Belgorod	9412359	Wave 3	25.02.2025	2
48	Bratsk	9411020	Wave 3	25.02.2025	2

49	Nikolay Zadornov	9901037	Wave 3	25.02.2025	2
50	Victor Konetsky	9301421	Wave 3	25.02.2025	2
51	Viktor Titov	9301407	Wave 3	25.02.2025	1
52	Pavel Chernysh	9301380	Wave 3	25.02.2025	1
53	Captain Kostichev	9301392	Wave 3	25.02.2025	1
54	Xanthos Eos	9231212	Wave 3	25.02.2025	0
55	Surrey Quays	9350654	Wave 3	25.02.2025	1
56	Nichole	9332822	Wave 3	25.02.2025	3
57	Crius	9251274	Wave 3	25.02.2025	1
58	Great Jacombo	9319703	Wave 3	25.02.2025	1
59	Chen Lu	9404948	Wave 3	25.02.2025	1
60	Mitzel	9233741	Wave 4	21.05.2025	1
61	Nan Feng Zhi Xing	9934498	Wave 4	21.05.2025	1
62	Tong Yuan	9638197	Wave 4	21.05.2025	0
63	Ocean 28	1021570	Wave 4	21.05.2025	0
64	Vladimir Asenyev	9901025	Wave 4	21.05.2025	3
65	Si He	9378618	Wave 4	21.05.2025	1
66	Lotus	9392822	Wave 4	21.05.2025	1
67	Ascendant	9248801	Wave 4	21.05.2025	3
68	Talisman	9292060	Wave 4	21.05.2025	3
69	Hyperion	9322968	Wave 4	21.05.2025	2
70	Saturn I	9655470	Wave 4	21.05.2025	2
71	Volga River	9435363	Wave 4	21.05.2025	0
72	Irtys River	9435375	Wave 4	21.05.2025	0
73	VF Tanker-3	9640516	Wave 4	21.05.2025	0

74	VF Tanker-4	9640528	Wave 4	21.05.2025	0
75	Kupava	9749154	Wave 4	21.05.2025	0
76	Cilicia	9171175	Wave 4	21.05.2025	0
77	Taimyr	9105140	Wave 4	21.05.2025	0
78	Savitri	9289752	Wave 4	21.05.2025	2
79	Venetians	9436018	Wave 5	20.07.2025	2
80	Jacklyn	9313498	Wave 5	20.07.2025	1
81	Sea Marine I	9255830	Wave 5	20.07.2025	0
82	Diva I	9297371	Wave 5	20.07.2025	3
83	Hulda	9290309	Wave 5	20.07.2025	2
84	Jaldhara	9304825	Wave 5	20.07.2025	4
85	Vision	9260067	Wave 5	20.07.2025	2
86	Nagarjuna	9299733	Wave 5	20.07.2025	3
87	Sandhya	9352195	Wave 5	20.07.2025	2
88	Himalaya	9314882	Wave 5	20.07.2025	3
89	Sea Honor	9315654	Wave 5	20.07.2025	2
90	Ru Yi	9345623	Wave 5	20.07.2025	4
91	Sealion I	9234501	Wave 5	20.07.2025	0
92	Achilles	9368223	Wave 5	20.07.2025	2
93	Hu Po	9319686	Wave 5	20.07.2025	1
94	Pearl	9630028	Wave 5	20.07.2025	3
95	Valera	9630004	Wave 5	20.07.2025	4
96	Sirius I	9285847	Wave 5	20.07.2025	2
97	Cordelia Moon	9297888	Wave 5	20.07.2025	2
98	Virat	9832559	Wave 5	20.07.2025	2

99	Themis	9264570	Wave 5	20.07.2025	1
100	Deneb	9301524	Wave 5	20.07.2025	1

Sources: EU sanction lists (Waves 1–5, Jun 2024 – Jul 2025); SeaSearcher vessel tracking database. Flag and name histories cc

leet — In-Depth Sample: Identity & Ownership Data (100 vess

FLAG CHANGES

Full Flag History
(since Feb 2022)

Bahamas → Cook Islands → Barbados → Sao Tome → St. Maarten

Russia

Russia

Russia → Panama → Russia

Panama → Russia

Germany → Saint Kitts and Nevis → Mongolia → Gabon → Tanzania

Marshall Island → Panama → Djibouti → Oman

Liberia → Gabon → Barbados → Comoros → Oman

Liberia → Gabon → Barbados → Comoros

Liberia → Gabon → Barbados

Liberia → Gabon → Barbados → Comoros → Oman

Russia

Russia

Marshall Island → Panama

Panama → Comoros

Russia

Libya → Cook Islands → Barbados → Sao Tome → Comoros → Sierra Leone

Marshall Islands → Cook Islands → Barbados → Comoros → Sao Tome →
Sierra Leone

Libya → Cook → Barbados → Comoros

Cameroon

Greece → Liberia → Marshall Islands → Guinea-Bissau → Tanzania

Liberia → Gabon → Djibouti → Comoros → Gambia

Bahamas → Singapore → Palau → Bonaire → Russia

Liberia → Gabon
Marshall Islands → Cook Islands → Tanzania → Comoros
Cyprus → Panama → Russia
Liberia → Gabon → Barbados → Comoros → Oman
Marshall Island → Panama → Cook Islands → Barbados → Comoros
Syria → Eswatini
Syria → Tanzania → Eswatini
Syria → Eswatini → Gambia → Togo
Liberia → Gabon → Barbados → Tanzania → Comoros → ? → Oman
Liberia → Gabon → Barbados → Oman
Liberia → Gabon → Barbados → Oman
Liberia → Gabon → Barbados → Comoros → Oman
Liberia → Gabon → Barbados → Comoros → Oman
Liberia → Gabon → Barbados → Comoros → Oman
Liberia → Gabon → Barbados → Comoros → Oman
Liberia → Gabon → Barbados → Sao Tome → Gambia
Liberia → Gabon → Barbados → Comoros → Oman
Liberia → Gabon → Barbados → Comoros → Oman
Indonesia → Cook Islands → Honduras → Tanzania → Comoros
Liberia → Gabon → Barbados → Comoros
Liberia → Gabon → Barbados → Comoros → Oman
Hong Kong → Marshall Islands → Barbados → Comoros → Gambia
Cyprus → Panama → Comoros → Gambia
Liberia → Gabon → Russia
Liberia → Gabon → Russia

Cyprus → Panama → Barbados → Comoros → Gambia
Cyprus → Panama → Barbados → Comoros → Gambia
Cyprus → Panama → Comoros → Gambia
Cyprus → Panama → Russia
Cyprus → Panama → Russia
Panama
Marshall Island → Panama → Comoros → Zimbabwe
Liberia → Marshall Islands → Hong Kong → Panama → Gambia → Cameroon
Saudi Arabia → Panama
Marshall Islands → Gabon → Gambia → Oman
Panama → Djibouti → Comoros → Gambia
Vietnam → Sierra Leone → Comoros → Gambia
China → Panama
China
Panama
Cyprus → Panama → Comoros → Gambia
Singapore → Panama → Russia
Bahamas → Panama
Malta → Saint Kitts and Nevis → Panama → Djibouti
Liberia → Gabon → Djibouti → Comoros → Gambia
Liberia → Gabon → Barbados → Comoros → Gambia
Russia → Palau → Russia
Russia
Russia
Russia

Russia
Russia
Russia
Russia
Marshall Islands → Gabon → Djibouti
Liberia → Panama → Palau → Mozambique → Cameroon
Liberia → Panama
Vietnam
Marshall Islands → Saint Kitts and Nevis → Panama → Comoros → Benin
Malta → Panama → Sao Tome
Malta → Saint Kitts and Nevis → Gabon → Panama → Guinea-Bissau
Liberia → Palau → Gambia
Marshall Islands → Gabon → Djibouti → Sao Tome → Sierra Leone
Liberia → Gabon → Panama
Liberia → Gabon → Panama → Palau → Benin
Bahamas → Liberia → Panama
Liberia → Panama → Gabon → Panama → Palau → Sierra Leone
Panama
Singapore → Saint Kitts and Nevis → Panama
Marshall Islands → Panama → Sierra Leone
Liberia → Gabon → Barbados → Comoros
Liberia → Gabon → Barbados → Comoros → Oman
Marshall Island → Panama → Comoros
Malta → Panama → Palau → Benin
Liberia → Panama → Comoros → Gambia

Panama → Palau
Vietnam → Sierra Leone

compiled manually. '→' denotes sequential change. Post-sanction columns reflect changes o

els | Waves 1–5 | Jun 2024 – Jul 2025)

Post-Sanction Flags	Total Name Changes
Cook Islands → Barbados → Sao Tome → St. Maarten	1
Russia	0
Gabon → Tanzania	1
Panama → Djibouti → Oman	1
Gabon → Barbados → Comoros → Oman	0
Gabon → Barbados → Comoros	0
Barbados	0
Gabon → Barbados → Comoros → Oman	0
Russia	0
Russia	1
Panama	1
Comoros	0
Russia	0
Cook Islands → Barbados → Sao Tome → Comoros → Sierra Leone	1
Cook Islands → Barbados → Comoros → Sao Tome → Sierra Leone	1
Cook → Barbados → Comoros	1
Cameroon	2
Guinea-Bissau → Tanzania	1
Gabon → Djibouti → Comoros → Gambia	1
Palau → Bonaire → Russia	2

Gabon	2
Cook Islands → Tanzania → Comoros	1
Panama → Russia	0
Barbados → Comoros → Oman	1
Barbados → Comoros	4
Eswatini	1
Eswatini	1
Eswatini → Gambia → Togo	1
Tanzania → Comoros → ? → Oman	1
Barbados → Oman	1
Barbados → Oman	1
Barbados → Comoros → Oman	1
Barbados → Comoros → Oman	1
Barbados → Comoros → Oman	1
Barbados → Comoros → Oman	1
Barbados → Sao Tome → Gambia	1
Barbados → Comoros → Oman	1
Barbados → Comoros → Oman	1
Honduras → Tanzania → Comoros	1
Barbados → Comoros	1
Barbados → Comoros → Oman	1
Barbados → Comoros → Gambia	2
Panama → Comoros → Gambia	0
Russia	1
Russia	1

Barbados → Comoros → Gambia	1
Barbados → Comoros → Gambia	0
Panama → Comoros → Gambia	0
Panama → Russia	0
Panama → Russia	0
Panama	0
Panama → Comoros → Zimbabwe	1
Panama → Gambia → Cameroon	2
Panama	1
Gabon → Gambia → Oman	1
Djibouti → Comoros → Gambia	2
Sierra Leone → Comoros → Gambia	2
Panama	0
China	0
Panama	0
Gambia	0
Panama → Russia	1
Panama	1
Djibouti	3
Comoros → Gambia	1
Barbados → Comoros → Gambia	1
Russia	1
Russia	0
Russia	0
Russia	0

Russia	0
Djibouti	0
Palau → Mozambique → Cameroon	4
Panama	1
Vietnam	0
Comoros → Benin	3
Sao Tome	2
Guinea-Bissau	2
Gambia	2
Sao Tome → Sierra Leone	2
Panama	2
Palau → Benin	2
Panama	3
Palau → Sierra Leone	3
Panama	0
Panama	1
Panama → Sierra Leone	3
Comoros	1
Oman	1
Comoros	1
Palau → Benin	1
Comoros → Gambia	2

Palau	0
Sierra Leone	1

ccurring after each vessel's individual designation date.

NAME CHANGES

Full Name History
(since Feb 2022)

Aris → Canis Power → N Cerna → Dhezi

Angara

Maria

Saam FSU

Koryak FSU

Louie → Hana → Kavya → Jun Ma

Fulmar → Andromeda Star → Feng Shou → Apar → Devika

NS Lotus → Legacy → Lavender

NS Spirit → Saga

NS Stream → Serenade

SCF Amur → Success → Solaris

Lady R

Neptun → Maia-1

Zhi Xian Zhi Xian → Hunter Star

Hebe → Daksha

Enisey

Samraa Alkhaleej → Vela Rain → Kelly Grace → Rizvel

Everglades → Ocean Amz → Ozanno

Alhani → Galian 2 → Delvina

Pelican → Turba → Robon → Bodhi

Houstan Star → Beks Aqua → Lunar Tide

Europchampion 2004 → Mianzimu → Dashan

LNG Pioneer → Pioneer Spirit → Pioneer → Sputnik Energy → Arctic Pioneer

Afra Crown → Danica → Alissa → Soufia 1
Piltene → Marabella Sun
Christophe de Margerie
NS Arctic → Altair → Amulet
Ridgebury Mary Selena → Mike R → Jal Fighter → Fighter Two → Peta Lumina → Boston Beacon
Souria → San Damian
Laodicea → San Cosmas → Monte Rosa
Finikia → San Severus → Monte Bianco
Korolev Prospect → Galaxy
Primorsky Prospect → Rigel → Primavera
NS Clipper → Cassiopeia → Carma
NS Commander → Constellation → Cavalier
Adygeya → Andromeda → Amazon
NS Concord → Callisto → Celt
NS Asia → Alliance → Arrow
SCF Pechora → Phoenix → Photon
Leonid Loza → Leo → Lynx
Nikolay Zuyev → Zenith
Pelagos One → Turbo Voyager → Range Vale
SCF Surgut → Sirius
SCF Samotlor → Saturn → Spartan
Sophie Schulte → Beks Sun → Life → Oasis
Yuri Senkevich
NS Bravo → Belgorod
NS Burgas → Bratsk

Samsung 2368 → Nikolay Zadornov
Victor Konetsky
Viktor Titov
Pavel Chernysh
Capitan Kostichev → Kapitan Kostichev
Mermar → Xanthos Eos
Clivia → Surrey Quays → Ruby Cross
Taurus Sun → Nicholas → Nichole
Khafji → Crius
Lionheart → Great Jacombo → Divya → Solea → Siraj
Pro Triumph → Bambu → Chen Lu → Thron
Henry → Hali → Olivia → Mitzel
Nan Feng Zhi Xing → Glory Ocean
Tong Yuan
Ocean 28
Vladimir Arsenyev
Pioneer Bay → Si He → Pioneer 1
Berica → Himalayan → Lotus
Seacrown 1 → Atacama → Mudan → Ascendant
Tavrishesky Bridge → Talisman
NS Power → Hyperion
SVL Unity → Saturn 1
Volga River
Irtys River
VF Tanker 3 → Veles

VF Tanker 4 → Poseidon S
Kupava
Ice Eagle → Cilicia
Taimyr
River Shiner → Ariadne → Arjuna → Savitri
Iridescent → Afragold → Huihai Indianocean → Jinjiang Experience → Venetians → Ocean Pearl → DG Hong Kong
Nemo → Jacklyn
Sea Marine 1
Godam → Parosea → Suleyman 1 → Diva 1
Seagrace → Thea → Hulda
Seamaster IV → Theseus → Jaldhara
Tornado → Juvenis → Vision
Antaios → Antaeus → Nagarjuna
Lugano → Lagoon → Sandhya
Amphitrite → Mystras → Himalaya → Runa
Sonangol Kassanje → Lila Orlando → Kapok → Sea Honor
Apostolos 2 → Morea → Tarang → Ru Yi → Elyte
Sealion 1 → Stabilis 1
Gullit → Achilles
Timberwolf → Epanastasea → Nemo 1 → Hu Po
Pskov → Pearl
Velikiy Novgorod → Valera
WonderSirius → Sirius 1
Seadancer → Cordelia Moon → Walrus
Crudesun → Valour → Virat

Themis → Nayara

Palmer → Deneb

Post-Sanction Names	Registered Company (Jurisdiction)
Canis Power → N Cerna → Dhezi	NB Shipping Company Limited (Russia)
Angara	NB Shipping Company Limited (Russia)
Maria	Ibex Shipping Inc. (Cyprus)
Saam FSU	Saam FSU Ltd. (Hong Kong)
Koryak FSU	Arctic Transshipment (Russia)
Hana → Kavya → Jun Ma	—
Andromeda Star → Feng Shou → Apar → Devika	Tulia Maritime (Seychelles)
NS Lotus → Legacy → Lavender	Azurite Shipholding Ltd. (Seychelles)
NS Spirit → Saga	Gismo Navigation (Seychelles)
NS Stream → Serenade	Pharos Seaways Company Ltd. (Seychelles)
SCF Amur → Success → Solaris	White Agate Marine SPC (Oman)
Lady R	MG Flot (Russia)
Maia-1	MG Flot (Russia)
Hunter Star	Guangdong Nanfeng Group Co., Ltd. (China)
Hebe → Daksha	Loire Shipping Inc. (Panama)
Enisey	Nord Project (Russia)
Vela Rain → Kelly Grace → Rizvel	Stella Brite Shipping (Marshall Islands)
Ocean Amz → Ozanno	Zorren Depth Shipping Ltd. (Marshall Islands)
Galian 2 → Delvina	Rocca International Ltd. (Marshall Islands)
Robon → Bodhi	Crystal Crest (Seychelles)
Beks Aqua → Lunar Tide	Winky International (Marshall islands)
Mianzimu → Dashan	Reef Marine Inc. (Seychelles)
Pioneer → Sputnik Energy → Arctic Pioneer	Zara Shipholding Company (Liberia)

Alissa → Soufia 1	Doxa Shipping Line Inc. (UAE)
Marabella Sun	Clarita Shipping Ltd. (Marshall Islands)
Christophe de Margerie	Zelitiko Shpping Comp. Ltd. (Cyrpus)
Altair → Amulet	Citrine Marine SPC (Oman)
Peta Lumina → Boston Beacon	Ealink Shipping Ltd. (Marshall Islands)
San Damian	Alhouda Holding Ltd. (Seychelles)
San Cosmas → Monte Rosa	?
San Severus → Monte Bianco	Bayaze Shipping Ltd. (Marshall Islands)
Galaxy	Anda Seaway Inc. (Seychelles)
Rigel → Primavera	White Agate Marine SPC (Oman)
Cassiopeia → Carma	Serpentine Marine SPC (Oman)
Constellation → Cavalier	Citrine Marine SPC (Oman)
Andromeda → Amazon	Citrine Marine SPC (Oman)
Callisto → Celt	Serpentine Marine SPC (Oman)
Alliance → Arrow	Citrine Marine SPC (Oman)
Phoenix → Photon	Carmi Tanker Ltd. (Seychelles)
Leo → Lynx	Serpentine Marine SPC (Oman)
Zenith	Kalsoy Shipping Ltd. (Liberia)
Turbo Voyager → Range Vale	Chatori Navigation Ltd. (Cook Islands)
Sirius	White Agate Marine SPC (Oman)
Saturn → Spartan	Citrine Marine SPC (Oman)
Life → Oasis	Sunny Maritime Services & Trading Inc. (Saint Kitts and Nevis)
Yuri Senkevich	Comitana Shipping HK Ltd. (Hong Kong)
Belgorod	NS Bravo Shpping Inc. (Liberia)
Bratsk	NS Burgas Shipping Inc. (Liberia)

Nikolay Zadornov	?
Victor Konetsky	Vimena Shipping HK Ltd. (Hong Kong)
Viktor Titov	Castellario Shipping HK Ltd. (Hong Kong)
Pavel Chernysh	Insania Shipping HK Ltd. (Hong Kong)
Capitan Kostichev → Kapitan Kostichev	Glimmer Shipping HK Ltd. (Hong Kong)
Mermar → Xanthos Eos	Merluza Group Ltd. (Hong Kong)
Surrey Quays → Ruby Cross	Brighton Pier Company Ltd. (Marshall Islands)
Nichole	Sea Swift Company Ltd. (Marshall Islands)
Crius	Crius Ltd. (Hong Kong)
Great Jacombo → Divya → Solea → Siraj	Davao Shipping Inc. (Mauritius)
Chen Lu → Thron	Acropora Marine Inc. (Seychelles)
Olivia → Mitzel	Frina Express Corp. (Seychelles)
Nan Feng Zhi Xing → Glory Ocean	Guangdong Nanfeng Group Co., Ltd. (China)
Tong Yuan	Tianjin International Marine Engineering Comp. Ltd. (China)
Ocean 28	Guangdong Yaqing Shipping Comp. Ltd. (China)
Vladimir Arsenyev	?
Si He → Pioneer 1	Loengo Shipping & Trader Ltd. (Seychelles)
Himalayan → Lotus	Gifted Peak Ltd. (Hong Kong)
Ascendant	Yuragi Ltd. (Mauritius)
Talisman	Ametrine Navigation Ltd. (Seychelles)
Hyperion	Rhona Marine Inc. (Seychelles)
Saturn 1	Prime Shipping LLC (Russia)
Volga River	SBK Dolina LLC (Russia)
Irtys River	SBK Dolina LLC (Russia)
VF Tanker 3 → Veles	Investnefttrade LLC (Russia)

VF Tanker 4 → Poseidon S	Investnefttrade LLC (Russia)
Kupava	Middle Volga Shipping Comp. (Russia)
Ice Eagle → Cilicia	RP-Shipping LLC (Russia)
Taimyr	Svarog Shipping & Trading Comp. Ltd. (UK)
River Shiner → Ariadne → Arjuna → Savitri	Sagara Ltd. (Seychelles)
Venetians → Ocean Pearl → DG Hong Kong	Eurus Shipping Company Ltd. (Hong Kong)
Jacklyn	Ocean Voyage Comp. Ltd. (Marshall Islands)
Sea Marine 1	Lan Dung Sea Freight Service Comp. Ltd. (Vietnam)
Diva 1	Morong Shipping Inc. (Mauritius)
Hulda	Sanda Goda Ltd. (Hong Kong)
Jaldhara	Naag Maritime Inc. (Seychelles)
Vision	?
Nagarjuna	Devta Ltd. (Seychelles)
Sandhya	Tunasan Shipping Inc. (Mauritius)
Himalaya → Runa	Shompen Shipping Ltd. (Seychelles)
Sea Honor	Changtai Shipping Ltd. (Marshall Islands)
Ru Yi → Elyte	Baitarani Shipping Ltd. (Seychelles)
Sealion 1 → Stabilis 1	Marine Spirit Global FZE (UAE)
Achilles	Siraj Maritime LLC (Oman)
Hu Po	Beryl Marine Inc. (Seychelles)
Pearl	Scalpay Shipping Ltd. (Liberia)
Valera	Boreray Shipping Ltd. (Liberia)
Sirius 1	Estrella Comp. Ltd. (Marshall Islands)
Cordelia Moon → Walrus	?
Virat	East Honest Hong Kong Ltd. (Hong Kong)

Themis → Nayara	Domi Lttle Ltd. (Hong Kong)
Deneb	Insist Line Ltd. (Seychelles)